

Polyethylene mulching increased mean maximum temperature at all observation times (data not shown). An increase of 7-13 °C in the mulched bed over the non-mulched bed was observed during the 3-wk period of solarization. Mulching significantly increased seedling growth (Table 1).

With regard to plant growth parameters, no significant differences were observed between treatments. The improved growth of seedlings in the solarized bed could have been due to the good control of plant parasitic nematodes, other soilborne pathogens, and weeds.

Good control of plant parasitic nematodes (50-87% reduction) was achieved in the solarized beds (Table 3). The decrease in root-knot nematode populations was most notable. Solarization controlled nematodes better than did organic amendment. ■

Water management

Supplemental irrigation for dry seeded upland rice

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Upland rice in Karnataka is often exposed to moisture stress due to dry spells that coincide with the critical growth stages of the crop. Supplemental irrigation using water from small tanks found all over the rainfed rice tract may increase rice yield.

We studied the effect of supplemental irrigation at various growth stages on grain yield of rice during the 1992 and 1994 wet seasons. The experiment consisted of rainfed rice and rice grown with supplemental irrigation (5 cm water depth) at booting, flowering, and grain-filling stages and their combination (see table for treatments). Daily irrigation from booting to 10 d before harvest was also one of the treatments. Due to high percolation in the unpuddled soil, the fields were flooded only for several hours after irrigation or heavy rainfall.

The 5.0- × 3.4-m plots were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Soil was silty clay loam with 0.4% slope. Plots were separated by well-compacted bunds and buffer channels.

Land was plowed and harrowed and direct seeded with rice cultivar Avinash (140 d) at the onset of the rains. A common fertilizer dose (100 kg N, 22 kg P, and 41 kg K ha⁻¹) was applied to all plots.

Total rainfall was 1150 in 1992 and 1135 mm in 1994 with 75 and 79 rainy days during the respective cropping season. Except for a dry spell of 11 d before booting in 1992, good rainfall was received during other stages in both years.

Irrigation at booting, alone or in combination with other stages, relieved the stress caused by the dry spell in 1992 and significantly increased yields. Irrigation only at flowering and grain-filling stages in 1992 and all irrigation treatments in 1994 did not increase yield. This was attributed to sufficient rainfall in 1994. During flowering and grain filling in 1992, plants were not stressed, even without irrigation.

Best results are obtained when timely supplemental irrigation is given only when dry spells occur during critical stages (booting, flowering, and grain filling). ■

Rice yield under sprinkler irrigation

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We investigated rice yield under sprinkler irrigation during three growing seasons 1991-93 in Turkey. The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications. Main plots were two irrigation intervals: 4d (A₁) and 8d (A₂). The subplots were irrigation depths (or amount): same amount of pan evaporation (B₁), 50% more than pan evaporation (B₂), and 100% more than pan evaporation (B₃). Plots were 12 m².

Seeds of rice variety Ergene (120 d) were drill-seeded in early May at 180 kg ha⁻¹ using 25-cm row spacing. N (150 kg ha⁻¹) was applied in two splits—1/2 basal and 1/2 60 d after planting. P (35.2 kg ha⁻¹) was applied during soil preparation. Weeds were controlled with two herbicide applications, before drilling and 40 d after drilling. Soil was sandy clay silt with 1.3% organic matter and pH 6.5.

All treatments received similar amounts of irrigation water until seedling emergence to ensure adequate stand establishment. Water use efficiency (WUE) was calculated by dividing grain yield (kg ha⁻¹) by total amount of water applied (mm) for the whole crop.

Irrigation interval has no significant effect on yield (see table). No interaction between irrigation interval and irrigation depth was observed. However, irrigation water depth influenced yield significantly.

As the amount of sprinkler irrigation water decreased, the yield decreased. B₃ had the highest yield while B₂ gave the highest WUE.

Grain yield of rice as influenced by supplemental irrigation management.^a Karnataka, India. 1992 and 1994.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			% increase over rainfed treatment
	1992	1994	Mean	
Rainfed	3.8	5.4	4.6	-
Irrigation at booting	5.3	5.4	5.4	17
Irrigation at flowering	4.4	4.9	4.7	1
Irrigation at grain filling	3.9	5.6	4.8	3
Irrigation at booting and flowering	5.4	5.7	5.5	20
Irrigation at flowering and grain filling	4.2	5.9	5.0	9
Irrigation at booting and grain filling	5.4	5.0	5.2	16
Irrigation at booting, flowering, and grain filling	5.5	5.2	5.3	16
Daily irrigation from booting up to 10 d before harvest	5.2	5.3	5.3	14
LSD (0.05)	1.3	ns ^b		

^a Water depth applied at each irrigation: 5 cm. ^bns = not significant.

Average yield of Ergene under flooded irrigation conditions (2000 mm water application) was about 6 t ha⁻¹. With the B3 treatment (1172 mm water application), yield was 4.7 t ha⁻¹.

Sprinkler irrigation can be thus used to increase WUE in conditions where water is scarce. Extra investment is, however, needed to install and operate the system. ■

Yield of rice under sprinkler irrigation. Edirne, Turkey. 1991-93.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Water applied (mm)				Water use efficiency (kg ha ⁻¹ mm ⁻¹)				
	1991	1992	1993	Mean	1991	1992	1993	Mean	1991	1992	1993	Mean	
4 d	A1B1	2.7 d	1.8 b	2.2 c	2.3 c	641	681	804	709	4.4	2.7	2.7	3.2
	A1B2	5.5 ab	3.2 abc	3.2 b	3.9 b	874	944	1004	940	6.3	3.3	3.1	4.2
	A1B3	5.9 a	3.6 ab	4.8 a	4.7 a	1107	1206	1203	1172	5.3	3.0	4.0	4.0
8 d	A2B1	3.7 cd	1.6 c	2.4 bc	2.5 c	641	681	804	709	5.7	2.3	2.9	3.6
	A2B2	4.6 bc	3.5 ab	4.4 a	4.2 ab	874	944	1004	940	5.3	3.7	4.4	4.4
	A2B3	4.8 ab	4.4 a	4.8 a	4.7 a	1107	1206	1203	1172	4.4	3.6	3.9	4.0
<i>F values</i>													
A	0.87	0.35	14.62	0.43									
B	24.36 ^{**b}	9.28 ^{**}	49.67 ^{**}	52.59 ^{**}									
A×B	4.18	0.50	3.77	0.32									
CD (0.05)	1.07	1.76	0.82	0.66									
CV (%)		12.49	18.06	12.03	16.55								

^aA: Irrigation interval: A1 = 4 d; A2 = 8 d. B: Irrigation depth (amount): B1 = same as pan evaporation; B2 = 50% of pan evaporation, B3 = 100% of pan evaporation. ^{b**} = significant at 1% level.

Farming systems

Effect of different rice cultures on crop yield in rice-based systems

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We investigated the performance of three rice cultures—(i) irrigated lowland (IL, rice seedlings transplanted in puddled soil under irrigated conditions); (ii) rainfed lowland (RL, crop established by dry seeding, followed by wet tillage at the 3-4 leaf stage under rainfed conditions [locally called halod]); and (iii) rainfed upland rice (DSR, rice dry seeded and raised as an upland crop under rainfed conditions)—and their subsequent effects on the yield of the

following upland crops of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*), and raya (*Brassica juncea*).

We conducted this experiment at the HPAU experimental farm in Palampur (32°6'N, 76°3'E, 1300 m altitude) during the 1993 and 1994 wet seasons. Soil was silty clay loam (Typic Hapludalf). Plots (5 × 3 m) were arranged in randomized complete block design with nine replications for rice and three replications for each upland crop. All crops received fertilizers at the recommended rates.

In both years, rice grain yield followed this trend: IL > RL > DSR. The differences were statistically significant. Grain yield of wheat and raya were highest in DSR and lowest in IL plots; linseed yield was not affected by the land preparation technique

adopted in the preceding rice crop.

The energy required to prepare the land after rice harvest was significantly affected by the land preparation technique used in rice. Puddling is the most intensive tillage practice in rice, followed by halod and dry tillage. Manual land preparation with the use of spades required about 967 h ha⁻¹ in IL, 633 h ha⁻¹ in RL, and 483 h ha⁻¹ in DSR. Considering that the energy of an adult worker equals 1.96 MJ human h⁻¹, land preparation after IL, RL, and DSR required 1895, 1241, and 947 MJ ha⁻¹, respectively. Thus, the energy required to prepare the seedbed after RL rice was about 2/3, and the energy needed for the crop after DSR was about 1/2 that of IL rice.

Rice in silty clay loam soil performed best under lowland irrigated conditions. But this rice culture did not favor the following crops of wheat and raya. They performed best after DSR. Linseed was unaffected by rice culture. Because wheat is next to rice in importance, appropriate tillage technology has to be developed to maximize crop yields in rice - wheat cropping systems. ■

Grain yield of crops (t ha⁻¹) in rice-based cropping systems involving three rice cultures.

Rice culture	Rice		Wheat		Linseed		Raya	
	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992
Irrigated lowland	4.2	4.5	3.0	3.3	1.2	1.3	0.9	1.0
Rainfed lowland	3.3	3.5	3.6	3.9	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4
Direct seeded rice	2.9	3.1	3.9	4.1	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.7
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	ns	ns	0.1	0.2